

Anexo. Artículos analizados en esta revisión de literatura.

Cita	Título	Revista	País	Universidad
(Flett et al., 2020)	App-based mindfulness meditation for psychological distress and adjustment to college in incoming university students: a pragmatic, randomised, waitlist-controlled trial	Psychology & Health	Nueva Zelanda	University of Otago
(Czajkowski et al., 2020)	Mindfulness for musicians: A mixed methods study investigating the effects of 8-week mindfulness courses on music students at a leading conservatoire	Musicae scientiae	Reino Unido	Guildhall School of Music and Drama
(Corti & Gelati, 2020)	Mindfulness and coaching to improve learning abilities in university students: A pilot study	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Italia	University of Naples Federico II
(Ahmad et al., 2020)	An eight-week, web-based mindfulness virtual community intervention for students' mental health: Randomized controlled trial	JMIR Mental Health	Canada	York University
(Reilly, 2020)	Developing our students' level of mindfulness during these unprecedented times	Journal of university teaching and learning practice	México	Universidad Panameric
(Oblitas et al., 2019)	Incidencia del mindfulness en el estrés académico en estudiantes universitarios: Un estudio controlado	Terapia psicológica	Perú	Universidad Autónoma del Perú
(Firth et al., 2019)	Mindfulness and self-efficacy in pain perception, stress and academic performance. The influence of mindfulness on cognitive processes	Psychology Research and Behavior Management	Noruega	Inland Norway University of Applied Science
(Simmons & Redman, 2018)	Teaching Mindfulness Online	Journal of the Australian and New Zealand Student Services Association	Australia	Charles Sturt University
(Mahalingam & Rabelo, 2019)	Teaching Mindfulness to Undergraduates: A Survey and Photovoice Study	Journal of Transformative Education	Estados Unidos	University of Michigan
(Froiland, 2018)	Promoting Gratitude and Positive Feelings About Learning Among Young Adults	Journal of Adult Development	Estados Unidos	Purdue University
(Schwind et al., 2017)	Mindfulness practice as a teaching-learning strategy in higher education: A qualitative exploratory pilot study	Nurse Education Today	Canada	Ryerson University
(Miller et al., 2017)	The Feasibility of Bringing Brief Mindfulness-Based Training to the University Classroom	Mindfulness	Canada	University of Windsor

(Sampl et al., 2017)	A Randomized Controlled Pilot Intervention Study of a Mindfulness-Based Self-Leadership Training (MBSLT) on Stress and Performance	Mindfulness	Austria	University of Innsbruck
(Goretzki & Zysk, 2017)	Using mindfulness techniques to improve student wellbeing and academic performance for university students: A pilot study	Journal of the Australian and New Zealand Student Services Association	Australia	University of South Australia (UniSA)
(Dvorakova et al., 2017)	Promoting healthy transition to college through mindfulness training with first-year college students: Pilot randomized controlled trial	Journal Of American College Health	Estados unidos	Pennsylvania State University
(Hjeltnes et al., 2015)	Facing the fear of failure: An explorative qualitative study of client experiences in a mindfulness-based stress reduction program for university students with academic evaluation anxiety	International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being	Noruega	University of Bergen
(Van der Riet et al., 2015)	Piloting a stress management and mindfulness program for undergraduate nursing students: Student feedback and lessons learned	Nurse Education Today	Australia	The University of Newcastle
(Bonamo et al., 2015)	The Influence of a Brief Mindfulness Exercise on Encoding of Novel Words in Female College Students	Mindfulness	Estados unidos	University of North Dakota
(Lauricella, 2014)	Mindfulness Meditation with Undergraduates in Face-to-Face and Digital Practice: a Formative Analysis	Mindfulness	Canada	University of Ontario
(Brunye et al., 2013)	Learning to relax: Evaluating four brief interventions for overcoming the negative emotions accompanying math anxiety	Learning and Individual Differences	Estados unidos	Tufts University
(Yamada & Victor, 2012)	The impact of mindful awareness practices on college student health, well-being, and capacity for learning: A pilot study	Psychology Learning and Teaching	Estados unidos	California State University
(Gómez et al., 2019)	El programa de mindfulness "aprendiendo a respirar" en adolescentes haciendo la transición a la universidad: ensayo piloto controlado aleatorizado	Revista de Psicología Clínica con Niños y Adolescentes	España	Universidad de Deusto
(Mascaro et al., 2016)	Meditation buffers medical student compassion from the deleterious effects of depression	Journal of Positive Psychology	Estados unidos	Universidad Emory
(Altinyelken, 2018)	Promoting the psycho-social well-being of international students through mindfulness:	Contemporary Buddhism	Holanda	Univ. Amsterdam

	a focus on regulating difficult emotions				
(Canby et al., 2015)	A Brief Mindfulness Intervention for Healthy College Students and Its Effects on Psychological Distress, Self-Control, Meta-Mood, and Subjective Vitality	Mindfulness	Estados unidos		Beloit College
(Cho et al., 2016)	The Effectiveness of Daily Mindful Breathing Practices on Test Anxiety of Students	Plos ONE	South korea		Yeungnam University
(Czajkowski & Greasley, 2015)	Mindfulness for singers: The effects of a targeted mindfulness course on learning vocal technique	British Journal of Music Education	United Kingdom		University of Leeds
(De Vibe et al., 2013)	Mindfulness training for stress management: a randomised controlled study of medical and psychology students	BMC Medical Education	Noruega		University of Oslo and the University of Tromsø
(De Bruin et al., 2015)	Mindfulness in Higher Education: Awareness and Attention in University Students Increase During and After Participation in a Mindfulness Curriculum Course	Mindfulness	Holanda		University of Amsterdam
(Ding et al., 2014)	Improving creativity performance by short-term meditation	Behavioral and Brain Functions	China		Dalian University of Technology (DUT)
(Eva & Thayer, 2017)	Learning to BREATHE: A Pilot Study of a Mindfulness-Based Intervention to Support Marginalized Youth	Journal of Evidence-Based Complementary & Alternative Medicine	Estados unidos		Seattle University
(Galante et al., 2018)	A mindfulness-based intervention to increase resilience to stress in university students (the Mindful Student Study): a pragmatic randomised controlled trial	Lancet Public Health	United Kingdom		University of Cambridge
(Lynch et al., 2018)	Mindfulness-Based Coping With University Life: A Randomized Wait-List Controlled Study	SAGE open	United Kingdom		University of Northampton
(Mrazek et al., 2013)	Mindfulness Training Improves Working Memory Capacity and GRE Performance While Reducing Mind Wandering	Psychological Science	Estados unidos		University of California
(Parcover et al., 2018)	Effects of a Brief Mindfulness Based Group Intervention On College Students	Journal of College Student Psychotherapy	Estados unidos		Loyola University Maryland,
(Ramasubramanian, 2017)	Mindfulness, stress coping and everyday resilience among emerging youth in a university setting: a mixed methods approach	International Journal of Adolescence and Youth	Estados unidos		Texas A&M University

(Ramler 2016)	et al.,	Mindfulness and the College Transition: The Efficacy of an Adapted Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Intervention in Fostering Adjustment among First-Year Students	Mindfulness	Estados unidos	College of Saint Benedict/Saint John's University
(Shahidi 2017)	et al.,	Effectiveness of mindfulness-based stress reduction on emotion regulation and test anxiety in female high school students	Journal of Education and Health Promotion	Irán	Isfahan University of Medical Sciences
(Wang & Liu, 2016)		Cultivate Mindfulness: A Case Study of Mindful Learning in an English as a Foreign Language Classroom	The IAFOR Journal of Education	China	Northeast university in the Mainland China